

REFINED THEORY OF SANDWICH BEAMS WITH PIEZOELECTRIC FACE SHEETS

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ABSTRACT: This paper presents a refined theory of sandwich beams containing piezoelectric face sheets. In the classical sandwich plate theory, face sheet thickness effect is not considered and the stresses are assumed to be uniform through the thickness of the face sheet. However, in sandwich beams with thick face sheets the variation of stresses through the thickness must be considered. In this paper equations for a sandwich beam with piezoelectric face sheets are derived using the principle of minimum potential energy. The equations for an adaptive sandwich beam structure with low shear modulus core are considered with the piezoelectric effect. The new theory is illustrated by considering both mechanical and electrical loading of a cantilever beam. The deflections and stresses are compared with that from classical sandwich theory.

KEYWORDS: piezoelectric material, sandwich beam, actuator, face sheet, core

INTRODUCTION

The analysis of adaptive or smart piezoelectric structures has been an important topic of research over the last two decades. When a piezoelectric material element is stressed electrically by a voltage, its dimensions change. Also when it is stressed mechanically by an external force, it generates an electric charge. Therefore the material can alter the structure's response through actuation and sensing. Of the different materials available for use in smart structures, only piezoelectric materials have the unique capability to be used effectively as both actuator and sensor elements. Other advantages of piezoelectric materials that help account for their wide spread popularity include: simple integration into the structure; a readily obtainable commercial supply of piezopolymers and piezoceramics; and familiarity in using these materials gained from previous applications in transducers. This paper is devoted to the development of a refined sandwich beam theory for smart piezoelectric composite beams. The scope of this paper is to formulate the refined theory, which can explain the static behavior under electrical loading or mechanical loading. This refined theory provides more accurate results for displacement, strain, and stress fields.

The experimental work of Baily and Hubbard (1985) is usually cited as the first application of piezoelectric materials as actuators for vibration control. Using a piezoelectric polymer film as the active element on a cantilever beam, they were able to demonstrate active damping of the first vibration mode. This new actuator application brought a renewed interest in the development of piezoelectric materials for advanced aerospace structures. Crawley and de Luis (1987) developed an induced strain actuator model for beams. They formulated static and dynamic analytical models based on the governing equations for beams with attached and embedded piezoelectric actuators to model extension and bending. Park and Chopra (1996) formulated one-dimensional models to predict the extension, bending, and the torsion behavior of beams under piezoelectric actuation. Sun and Zhang (1995) proposed an adaptive sandwich structure consisting of stiff face sheets and a piezoelectric core. Wang and Quek (2000) presented their research on the free vibration of a piezoelectric sandwich beam

structure, in which the piezoelectric effect on the resonance frequencies of the structure and the distribution of the electric potential are studied and analyzed.

A REFINED SANDWICH BEAM THEORY

Displacements and Strains in the Core and Face Sheet

Consider a sandwich beam with core thickness $2c$, and top and bottom face-sheets with thickness, h_1 and h_2 respectively.

The core displacements can be expressed in the form:

$$\begin{aligned} u(x, z) &= u_0(x) + z\psi \\ w(x, z) &= w_0(x) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1 Depiction of displacement field in a sandwich beam

In Eqn.1 u_0 is the displacements of points along the x -axis, and ψ is the rotation of the core cross section. The transverse displacement is assumed to be constant through the core thickness, thus the compression or expansion of the core is neglected. Furthermore the shear deformation in the core is included by the non-vanishing shear term γ_{xz} , which is given by:

$$\gamma_{xz} = \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} = \psi + \theta \quad (2)$$

where θ denotes the slope $\frac{dw}{dx}$.

The top and bottom face sheets are assumed to deform according to Euler-Bernoulli classical beam theory. That is, plane sections normal to the beam axis remain plane and normal to the deformed beam axis. Coordinates z_1 and z_2 for top and bottom face-sheets can be defined as $z_1 = z - c$ and $z_2 = z + c$ (see Fig. 1). The displacements of points in the face sheet are derived as follows;

Top face-sheet:

$$\begin{aligned} u(x, z_1) &= u_0 + c\psi - z_1\theta & 0 \leq z_1 \leq h_1 \\ w(x, z_1) &= w_0(x) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Bottom face-sheet:

$$\begin{aligned} u(x, z_2) &= u_0 - c\psi - z_2\theta & -h_2 \leq z_2 \leq 0 \\ w(x, z_2) &= w_0(x) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

It is assumed that the face-sheets carry only the normal stresses σ_x and the core carries only the shear stress τ_{xz} as in the conventional sandwich beam theory. Therefore the normal stresses in the core and the shear stresses in the face-sheet are ignored. The normal strains in the face-sheets are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_x(x, z_1) &= \varepsilon_{x0} + c\psi_{,x} - z_1\theta_{,x} \text{ for top face-sheet} \\ \varepsilon_x(x, z_2) &= \varepsilon_{x0} - c\psi_{,x} - z_2\theta_{,x} \text{ for bottom face-sheet} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

In Eqn.5 and what follows a comma followed by a subscript x denotes differentiation with respect to x .

Force and Moment Resultants

The sandwich beam is assumed to have a piezoelectric material as the face-sheet. The constitutive equation for the piezoelectric material is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_z \\ \sigma_{zx} \end{bmatrix} &= \begin{bmatrix} c_{11} & c_{13} \\ c_{13} & c_{33} \\ & & c_{44} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_{1,1} \\ u_{3,3} \\ u_{3,1} + u_{1,3} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} e_{31} \\ e_{33} \\ e_{15} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \phi_{,1} \\ \phi_{,3} \end{bmatrix} \\ \begin{bmatrix} D_1 \\ D_3 \end{bmatrix} &= \begin{bmatrix} & e_{15} \\ e_{31} & e_{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_{1,1} \\ u_{3,3} \\ u_{3,1} + u_{1,3} \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{11} & \\ & \varepsilon_{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \phi_{,1} \\ \phi_{,3} \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

The normal stresses in the face-sheet are derived as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_x(x, z_1) &= c_{11}\varepsilon_x(x, z_1) + e_{31}\phi_{,3} = c_{11}(\varepsilon_{x0} + c\psi_{,x} - z_1\theta_{,x}) + e_{31}\phi_{,3} \text{ for top face-sheet} \\ \sigma_x(x, z_2) &= c_{11}\varepsilon_x(x, z_2) + e_{31}\phi_{,3} = c_{11}(\varepsilon_{x0} - c\psi_{,x} - z_2\theta_{,x}) + e_{31}\phi_{,3} \text{ for bottom face sheet} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

We define the axial force resultant P , the bending moment resultants M and the transverse shear force resultant V_z as follows. Since the core does not carry any normal stresses, the expressions for the axial force and bending moments can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} P(x) &= \int_{-h_2}^0 \sigma_x(x, z_2) dz_2 + \int_0^{h_1} \sigma_x(x, z_1) dz_1 \\ M(x) &= \int_{-h_2}^0 (-c + z_2) \sigma_x(x, z_2) dz_2 + \int_0^{h_1} (-c + z_1) \sigma_x(x, z_1) dz_1 \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

$$V_z(x) = \int_{-c}^{+c} \tau_{xz}(x, z) dz$$

Similarly the bending moment can be split into two different contributions as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} M &= M_0 + M_f \\ M_0 &= \int_{-h_2}^0 (-c) \sigma_x(x, z_2) dz_2 + \int_0^{h_1} c \sigma_x(x, z_1) dz_1 \\ M_f &= \int_{-h_2}^0 z_2 \sigma_x(x, z_2) dz_2 + \int_0^{h_1} z_1 \sigma_x(x, z_1) dz_1 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

From Eqn.9 M_f can be thought of as the moment of the face-sheet normal stresses about the corresponding core/face-sheet interface. M_0 is the moment of axial forces, if the axial force resultants are resolved to act at the corresponding interface. For thin face-sheets the moment term M_f can be neglected in comparison to M_0 .

We can derive the constitutive equation for sandwich beam with piezoelectric face-sheet as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} P \\ M_0 \\ M_f \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A & B & C \\ B & D & E \\ C & E & F \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{x0} \\ \psi_{,x} \\ \kappa \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} P_t^p + P_b^p \\ c(P_t^p - P_b^p) \\ M_t^p - M_b^p \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

where κ is used to denote the beam curvature $-\theta_{,x}$.

The definition of the various coefficients in Eqn.10 is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} A &= A_1 + A_2 & A_1 &= \int_0^{h_1} c_{11} dz_1 & A_2 &= \int_{-h_2}^0 c_{11} dz_2 \\ B &= c(A_1 - A_2) & C &= c_1 + c_2 & C_1 &= \int_0^{h_1} z_1 c_{11} dz_1 & C_2 &= \int_{-h_2}^0 z_2 c_{11} dz_2 \\ D &= c^2(A_1 + A_2) & E &= c(C_1 - C_2) \\ F &= F_1 + F_2 & F_1 &= \int_0^{h_1} z_1^2 c_{11} dz_1 & F_2 &= \int_{-h_2}^0 z_2^2 c_{11} dz_2 \\ P_t^p &= e_{31} \int_0^{h_1} \phi_{,3} dz_1 & P_b^p &= e_{31} \int_{-h_2}^0 \phi_{,3} dz_2 & M_t^p &= e_{31} \int_0^{h_1} \phi_{,3} dz_1 & M_b^p &= e_{31} \int_{-h_2}^0 \phi_{,3} dz_2 \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

For a symmetric sandwich beam (symmetric about the x-y plane) $A_1 = A_2$, $C_1 = -C_2$, $F_1 = F_2$.

Therefore $A = 2A_1$, $B=C=0$, $D = c^2 A$, $E = 2cC_1$, and $F = 2F_1$

The shear force resultant V_z can also be split into two components V_c carried by the core and V_f carried by the face-sheets:

$$\begin{aligned} V_z &= V_c + V_f \\ V_c &= \int_{-c}^{+c} \tau_{xz}(x, z) dz \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

$$V_f = \int_0^{h_1} \tau_{xz}(x, z_1) dz_1 + \int_{-h_2}^0 \tau_{xz}(x, z_2) dz_2$$

Typically the core will carry a significant portion of the total shear force. From Eqn.2 we note that the shear strain in the core is independent of z . Therefore the shear force can be expressed in terms of deformation as

$$V_c = 2cG_c(\psi + \theta) \quad (13)$$

where G_c is the core shear modulus

Equilibrium Equation using the Principle of Minimum Potential Energy

We will apply the principle of minimum potential energy to derive the equations of equilibrium. The total potential energy of the beam is $\Pi = U + V$. The total potential energy is composed of the strain energy U in the entire beam and the potential energy V of the external forces acting on beam. The variation of Π with respect to the deformation should be equal to zero, i.e., $\delta\Pi = 0$.

The expression for strain energy density is given by

$$U_0 = \frac{1}{2} \sigma_{xx} \varepsilon_x + \frac{1}{2} G_c \gamma_{xz}^2 \quad (14)$$

The shear strain energy in the face-sheets is ignored as in the case of Euler-Bernoulli beam theory and we only consider shear strain energy in the core. The strain energy per unit length of the beam is given by

$$U_L = \int_{-(c+h_2)}^{c+h_1} U_0 dz \quad (15)$$

Substituting for the strains from Eqn.2 into Eqn.14 and then using Eqn.15 we obtain

$$U_L = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{x0} & \psi_{,x} & \kappa \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} A & B & C \\ B & D & E \\ C & E & F \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{x0} \\ \psi_{,x} \\ \kappa \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} P_t^p + P_b^p \\ c(P_t^p - P_b^p) \\ M_t^p - M_b^p \end{bmatrix} + \frac{1}{2} S(\psi + \theta)^2 \quad (16)$$

where the transverse shear stiffness $S = 2cG_c$. Using the constitutive relations Eqn.10, Eqn.16 can be expressed as

$$U_L = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{x0} & \psi_{,x} & \kappa \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} P \\ M_0 \\ M_f \end{bmatrix} + \frac{1}{2} S(\psi + \theta)^2 \quad (17)$$

The potential energy of the external forces acting on the beam can be expressed as:

$$V = - \int_0^L (p_x u_0 + p_z w_0) dx \quad (18)$$

where p_x and p_z are the axial force and transverse force per unit length acting along the beam axis. The variation of Π , $\delta\Pi$, can be expressed as

$$\delta\Pi = \int_0^L \left[P \delta\varepsilon_{x0} + M_0 \delta\psi_{,x} + M_f \delta\kappa + V_z (\delta\psi + \delta\theta) \right] dx - \int_0^L (p_x \delta u_0 + p_z \delta w_0) dx = 0 \quad (19)$$

Using integration by parts we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(P \delta u_0 + M_0 \delta\psi - M_f \delta\theta + \left(\frac{dM_f}{dx} + V_c \right) \delta w_0 \right) \Big|_0^L \\ & - \int_0^L \left(\frac{dP}{dx} \delta u_0 + \frac{dM_0}{dx} \delta\psi + \frac{d^2 M_f}{dx^2} \delta w_0 - V_c \delta\psi + \frac{dV_c}{dx} \delta w_0 \right) dx \\ & - \int_0^L (p_x \delta u_0 + p_z \delta w_0) dx = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

Since Eqn.20 must be true for any arbitrary variation in u_0 , ψ and w , the coefficients of δu_0 , $\delta\psi$ and δw , should be identically equal to zero:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dP}{dx} + p_x &= 0 \\ \frac{dM_0}{dx} - V_c &= 0 \\ \frac{d^2 M_f}{dx^2} + \frac{dV_c}{dx} + p_z &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

Eqn.21 are the three equilibrium equations for a sandwich beam with thick face sheets. From the boundary terms in Eqn.20 one can identify the boundary conditions as:

- Specify P or u_0 ,
- Specify M_0 or ψ ,
- Specify M_f or θ ,
- Specify $\left(\frac{dM_f}{dx} + V_c \right)$ or w_0 .

Thus there are four boundary conditions at each end of the sandwich beam. In the last boundary condition, $\left(\frac{dM_f}{dx} + V_c \right)$ can be replaced by $V_f + V_c$.

Thus the last boundary condition can be restated as: Specify the total shear force V_z or w_0 . The sandwich beam theory presented in the previous section includes the bending moment M_f carried by the face sheet. In a simplified sandwich beam theory, M_f can be

neglected, because it is much smaller than M_0 . Then there will be only 6 boundary conditions as shown in the Fig. 2 below:

Fig. 2 Boundary condition for classical sandwich beam

The constitutive equations for sandwich beam with piezoelectric face-sheet are as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} P \\ M \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ B & D \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{x0} \\ \psi_{,x} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} P_t^p + P_b^p \\ c(P_t^p - P_b^p) \end{bmatrix} \quad (22)$$

$$V_c = G_c(\psi + \theta)$$

The strain energy per unit length of the beam is given by:

$$U_L = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^L \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{x0} & \psi_{,x} \end{bmatrix} \left(\begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ B & D \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{x0} \\ \psi_{,x} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} P_t^p + P_b^p \\ c(P_t^p - P_b^p) \end{bmatrix} \right) dx + \frac{1}{2} S(\psi + \theta)^2 \quad (23)$$

The equations of equilibrium can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dP}{dx} + p_x &= 0 \\ \frac{dM}{dx} - V_c &= 0 \\ \frac{dV_c}{dx} + p_z &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

The equation of equilibrium can be expressed in terms of displacements by substituting for the force resultants in Eqn.24 from Eqn.22.

FORMULATION OF SANDWICH BEAM UNDER ELECTRICAL LOADING

Consider a cantilevered sandwich beam of length L subjected to electric potential V on the top and bottom at the each piezoelectric face sheet. We assumed that the beam is fixed at $x=0$ in such a way that both $\psi(0)$ and $\theta(0)$ are equal to zero. It is assumed that the beam is symmetric ($B=0, C=0$). The mechanical loading is nonexistent, i.e., $p_z = p_x = 0$

Fig. 3 Adaptive cantilevered sandwich beam under electrical loading

Integrating the 3rd equation in the equilibrium equations Eqn.21 we obtain

$$\frac{dM_f}{dx} + V_c = C_1 \quad (25)$$

It is noted that $V_c = \frac{dM_c}{dx}$. Substituting for V_c in Eqn.25 and integrate one more time we obtain:

$$M_f + M_c = C_1 x + C_2 \quad (26)$$

The constants C_1 and C_2 are equal to zeros due to the absence of external forces. Substituting for M_c and M_f from the constitutive relations Eqn.10

$$\begin{aligned} M_c &= D\psi_{,x} + E\kappa + c(P_t^p - P_b^p) \\ M_f &= E\psi_{,x} + F\kappa + (M_t^p - M_b^p) \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

Then we obtain

$$(D + E) \frac{d^2\psi}{dx^2} - (E + F) \frac{d^2\theta}{dx^2} = 0 \quad (28)$$

$$\psi = \frac{E + F}{D + E} \theta + C_3 x + C_4 \quad (29)$$

As derived earlier, $V_c = \frac{dM_c}{dx}$. We can obtain Eqn.30 by substituting Eqn.27 and Eqn.13 for V_c :

$$\frac{d}{dx} [D\psi_{,x} + E\kappa + c(P_t^p - P_b^p)] - S(\psi + \theta) = 0 \quad (30)$$

$$\frac{d^2\theta}{dx^2} + \frac{S}{E} \theta - \frac{D}{E} \frac{d^2\psi}{dx^2} + \frac{E}{S} \psi = 0 \quad (31)$$

Substituting for $\psi, \psi_{,x}$ from Eqn.29 into Eqn.31

$$\frac{d^2\theta}{dx^2} + \frac{S}{E}\theta - \frac{D}{E}\left(\frac{E+F}{D+E}\frac{d^2\theta}{dx^2}\right) + \frac{E}{S}\left(\frac{E+F}{D+E}\theta + C_3x + C_4\right) = 0 \quad (32)$$

Then we can derive a second order differential equation in $\theta(x)$ as

$$\frac{d^2\theta}{dx^2} - \lambda^2\theta = -\frac{S(D+E)}{E^2 - DF}(C_3x + C_4) \quad (32)$$

where

$$\lambda = \left\{ \frac{S(D+2E+F)}{DF - E^2} \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

General solution for $\theta(x)$ is given by

$$\theta(x) = C_5e^{\lambda x} + C_6e^{-\lambda x} - \frac{(D+E)}{(D+2E+F)}C_3x - \frac{D+E}{D+2E+F}C_4 \quad (33)$$

The constant C_4 can be determined from the boundary condition $\psi(0) = 0$. By the boundary condition $M_0(L) = 0$ and $M_f = 0$, C_3 can be determined. The constants C_5 and C_6 can be obtained from the boundary conditions $\theta(0) = 0$ and $M_f(L) = M_0(L) = 0$.

$$w(x) = \frac{C_5}{\lambda}e^{\lambda x} - \frac{C_6}{\lambda}e^{-\lambda x} - \frac{(D+E)}{(D+2E+F)}C_3\frac{x^2}{2} - \frac{D+E}{D+2E+F}C_4x + C_7 \quad (34)$$

The boundary condition $w(0) = 0$ is used to determine C_7 . Then the constants can be derived as

$$C_5 = \frac{\alpha + \beta}{2\lambda \cosh(\lambda L)} \quad C_6 = \frac{-(\alpha + \beta)}{2\lambda \cosh(\lambda L)} \quad C_7 = \frac{-(\alpha + \beta)}{\lambda^2 \cosh(\lambda L)} \quad C_4 = 0 \quad (35)$$

Then the deflection and the slope expressions are

$$w(x) = \frac{\alpha + \beta}{\lambda^2 \cosh(\lambda L)} (\cosh(\lambda x) - 1) - \alpha \frac{x^2}{2} \quad (36)$$

$$\theta(x) = \frac{\alpha + \beta}{\lambda \cosh(\lambda L)} (\sinh(\lambda x)) - \alpha x \quad (37)$$

where

$$\alpha = \frac{(M_b^p - M_t^p) + c(P_b^p - P_t^p)}{D + 2E + F}$$

$$\beta = \frac{cE(P_b^p - P_t^p) - D(M_b^p - M_t^p)}{DF - E^2}$$

$$\lambda = \left\{ \frac{S(D + 2E + F)}{DF - E^2} \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (38)$$

NUMERICAL RESULTS FOR A SANDWICH BEAM UNDER ELECTRICAL LOADING

The results are illustrated using an example of a sandwich beam with PZT 5H. The detailed material properties are shown at Table 1. The face sheet thickness and the core shear modulus are varied.

Table 1 Material properties for sandwich beam

PZT 5H (face sheet)					Core			
Elastic constants ($10^3 N/mm^2$)					Piezoelectric constants ($10^{-6} C/mm^2$)			Shear modulus (N/mm^2)
c_{11}	c_{12}	c_{13}	c_{33}	c_{44}	e_{31}	e_{33}	e_{15}	G_c
126	79.5	84.1	117	23	-6.5	23.3	17	$\frac{c_{11}}{50} - \frac{c_{11}}{400}$

The refined theory developed in this chapter is applied to the problem of cantilever sandwich beam subjected to an electric potential ($\pm 20V$) on the top and bottom piezoelectric face sheet. The maximum deflection of the sandwich beam is investigated and its variation with face sheet thickness and shear modulus G_c in core is studied. The results are compared to the results from the classical theory that does not consider face sheet thickness effects.

Fig. 4: Face sheet thickness vs. maximum deflection at tip for sandwich beams with different core shear modulus.

The change of face sheet thickness from 1.2 mm to 0.4 mm makes the maximum deflection increase by 351%. For a thickness of 0.4 mm, the difference in deflection between the refined theory and the classical theory is 8.1%. And also in the deflection for $h=1.2$ mm, there is a 33.8 % difference between the refined theory and the classical theory. From Fig. 4, it is observed that there is a significant difference in deflection between the refined theory and the classical theory for thicker beams. It can also be noted that the maximum deflection is over predicted by the classical theory.

Fig. 5 Deflection curves for different face sheet thicknesses for $Gc=c11/400$

In Fig. 5, the deflection curves for different face sheet thicknesses, 0.4 mm and 1.2 mm, are presented. The results are compared with that of classical sandwich beam theory. For thin face sheets, the deflection difference is getting closer. When the thickness is changes from 1.2 mm to 0.4 mm, the tip deflection increase up to 370%. Even though the electrical potentials have same values, the electrical field, which is the real input, is proportional to $1/h$.

Fig. 6 Axial stress distribution in top face sheet with respect to the change of thickness

The stress in the sandwich beam can be obtained using Eqn.7. The stress distribution in left fixed end under electrical load is calculated for different face sheet thickness ranging from 0.4 mm to 1.2 mm as shown Fig. 6. As shown Fig. 6, maximum stress occurs at the bottom of face sheet. It is observed that a reduction in thickness makes the stress to increase at the bottom of top face sheet. Therefore, when face sheet thickness is changed from 0.4 mm to 1.2 mm, maximum stress does not change significantly. But as it can be seen from Fig. 5, the change in deflection will be up to 351%.

FORMULATION OF SANDWICH BEAM UNDER MECHANICAL LOADING

Consider a cantilevered sandwich beam of length $L=100$ mm subjected to uniformly distributed loading p applied on the top at the piezoelectric face sheet. It is assumed that voltage is not applied at piezoelectric face sheet. We assume that the beam is fixed at $x=0$ in such a way that both $\psi(0)$ and $\theta(0)$ are equal to zero. Additionally we will consider that $M_f(0) = 0$ instead of $\theta(0) = 0$. This B.C. means that the face sheet is not fixed at the left-end. It is assumed that the beam is symmetric ($B=0, C=0$). And only the mechanical load exists, i.e., $p_z = -p_0 = W$.

Fig. 7 Adaptive cantilevered sandwich beam under mechanical loading

Integrating the 3rd equation of the equilibrium Eqn.21 we obtain

$$\frac{dM_f}{dx} + V_c = Wx + C_1 \quad (39)$$

It is noted that $V_c = \frac{dM_c}{dx}$. Substituting for V_c in Eqn.39 and integrating one more time we obtain:

$$M_f + M_c = \frac{W}{2}x^2 + C_1x + C_2 \quad (40)$$

As shear force and moment are zero at $x=L$, $C_1 = -WL$ $C_2 = \frac{WL^2}{2}$

Substituting for M_c and M_f from the constitutive relations Eqn.10

$$\begin{aligned} M_c &= D\psi_{,x} + E\kappa \\ M_f &= E\psi_{,x} + F\kappa \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

Substituting for ψ, ψ_{xx}

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^2\theta}{dx^2} - \frac{D}{E(D+E)}[(E+F)\frac{d^2\theta}{dx^2} + Wx - WL] + \frac{S}{E}\theta \\ + \frac{S}{E(D+E)}[(E+F)\theta + \frac{W}{6}x^3 - \frac{WL}{2}x^2 + \frac{WL^2}{2}x + C_3] = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

Then we obtain a second order differential equation in $\theta(x)$

$$\frac{d^2\theta}{dx^2} - \lambda^2\theta = \frac{1}{E^2 - DF} [DWx - DWL - S(\frac{W}{6}x^3 - \frac{WL}{2}x^2 + \frac{WL^2}{2}x + C_3)] \quad (46)$$

where

$$\lambda = \left\{ \frac{S(D+2E+F)}{DF - E^2} \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

General solution for $\theta(x)$ is given by

$$\theta(x) = C_8 e^{\lambda x} + C_9 e^{-\lambda x} + \alpha x^3 + \beta x^2 + \gamma x + \delta + \frac{1}{\lambda^2} \frac{S}{(E^2 - DF)} C_3 \quad (47)$$

$$w(x) = \frac{C_8}{\lambda} e^{\lambda x} - \frac{C_9}{\lambda} e^{-\lambda x} + \frac{\alpha}{4} x^4 + \frac{\beta}{3} x^3 + \frac{\gamma}{2} x^2 + (\delta + \frac{1}{\lambda^2} \frac{S}{(E^2 - DF)} C_3)x + C_{10} \quad (48)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha &= \frac{SW}{6\lambda^2(E^2 - DF)}, \quad \beta = \frac{-SWL}{2\lambda^2(E^2 - DF)} \\ \gamma &= \frac{1}{\lambda^2(E^2 - DF)} \left(\frac{SW}{\lambda^2} + \frac{SWL^2}{2} - DW \right), \quad \delta = \frac{WL}{\lambda^2(E^2 - DF)} \left(D - \frac{S}{\lambda^2} \right) \end{aligned}$$

Case 1: $\theta(0) = 0$

The constant C_3 will be zero from BC. By using the BCs, $w(0) = \theta(0) = M_f(L) = 0$ the constants C_8, C_9, C_{10} can be determined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} C_8 = -\frac{(e^{-\lambda L}\delta - H/\lambda)}{2 \cosh(\lambda L)}, \quad C_9 = -\frac{(H/\lambda + e^{\lambda L}\delta)}{2 \cosh(\lambda L)}, \quad C_{10} = \frac{1}{\lambda \cosh(\lambda L)} \left[-\frac{H}{\lambda} - \delta \sinh(\lambda L) \right] \\ \text{where } H = -(3\alpha L^2 + 2\beta L + \gamma) \end{aligned} \quad (49)$$

We substitute Eqn.49 into Eqn.47 and Eqn.48 to obtain slop $\theta(x)$ and deflection $w(x)$ as

$$\theta(x) = -\frac{(e^{-\lambda L}\delta - H/\lambda)}{2 \cosh(\lambda L)} e^{\lambda x} - \frac{(H/\lambda + e^{\lambda L}\delta)}{2 \cosh(\lambda L)} e^{-\lambda x} + \alpha x^3 + \beta x^2 + \gamma x + \delta \quad (50)$$

$$w(x) = -\frac{(e^{-\lambda L} \delta - H/\lambda)}{2\lambda \cosh(\lambda L)} e^{\lambda x} + \frac{(H/\lambda + e^{\lambda L} \delta)}{2\lambda \cosh(\lambda L)} e^{-\lambda x} + \frac{\alpha}{4} x^4 + \frac{\beta}{3} x^3 + \frac{\gamma}{2} x^2 + \delta x + \frac{1}{\lambda \cosh(\lambda L)} \left[-\frac{H}{\lambda} - \delta \sinh(\lambda L) \right] \quad (51)$$

Case2 $M_f(0) = 0$

In this case we change the BC at $x=0$. We specify that $M_f(0) = 0$ instead of specifying $\theta(0) = 0$. It means that top and bottom face sheets are not fixed at the left end.

We can obtain constants C_3, C_8, C_9, C_{10} from the BCs we obtain

$$w(0) = M_f(0) = M_f(L) = \psi(0) = 0.$$

Case 3 classical sandwich beam theory

Consider Fig. 2 and Eqn.23 for the response of a sandwich beam subjected to mechanical loading only and analyzed by the classical sandwich beam theory. In this theory face sheet is considered as very thin. A uniform loading of p_0 is considered.

The constitutive equation for sandwich beam can be expressed as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} P \\ M \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ B & D \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{x0} \\ \psi_{,x} \end{bmatrix} \quad V_c = 2cG_c(\psi + \theta) \quad (52)$$

The equilibrium Eqn.21 for a sandwich beam can be simplified as follows

$$\frac{dP}{dx} = 0 \quad \frac{dM}{dx} - V_c = 0 \quad \frac{dV_c}{dx} + p_z = 0 \quad (53)$$

By the similar procedure

$$\theta = \frac{Wx - WL}{S} - \left(\frac{Wx^3}{6D} - \frac{WL}{2D} x^2 + \frac{WL^2}{2D} x \right) \quad (54)$$

Integrating Eqn.54 with respect to x .

$$w = \frac{1}{S} \left(\frac{Wx^2}{2} - WLx \right) - \frac{1}{D} \left(\frac{Wx^4}{24} - \frac{WLx^3}{6} + \frac{WL^2}{4} x^2 \right) + C_4 \quad (55)$$

Applying BC $w(0) = 0$ we find that $C_4 = 0$.

$$\text{The tip deflection } w(L) = -\frac{WL^2}{2S} - \frac{WL^4}{8D} \quad (56)$$

NUMERICAL RESULTS OF SANDWICH BEAM UNDER MECHANICAL LOADING

The formulae for deflection and stress can be obtained by our derivation for cases 1 through 3. The results are illustrated using an example of a sandwich beam with PZT 5H. The detailed material properties are shown in Table 1. The face sheet thickness and the core shear

modulus are varied. The suggested theory is applied to the problem of cantilevered sandwich beam subjected to uniformly distributed load W on the top piezoelectric face sheet. The deflection and stress field in the sandwich beam are investigated as a function of face sheet thickness and core shear modulus G_c . The results are compared to the results from the classical sandwich theory, which does not consider the variation of displacement and stresses within the face sheet.

Fig. 8 Deflection by sandwich beam theories when $h=1.2 \text{ mm}$ & $G_c = c_{11} / 50 \text{ N/mm}^2$

Fig. 9 Deflection by sandwich beam theories when $h=0.4 \text{ mm}$ & $G_c = c_{11} / 50 \text{ N/mm}^2$

From Fig. 8 and 9, it can be seen that the classical theory over predicts deflection. The difference between the two theories is pronounced for the case of a thicker face sheets.

Fig. 10 Axial stresses in top face sheet in a cantilevered sandwich beam when face sheet thickness = 0.8mm and $G_c = c_{11} / 50$

Refined theory can also show the variation of axial stresses through thickness of the face. However, the classical theory assumes uniform stresses distribution in the face sheet.

CONCLUSIONS

In the present paper a refined sandwich beam theory has been presented, which takes into account the effect of face sheet thickness for both electrical and mechanical loading. A comparison with classical sandwich beam theory has been presented. It is concluded that the refined sandwich beam theory can provide more accurate solution for deflection and also discern between different types of boundary conditions compared to the classical theory.

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